

was very high in Turners Asbestos Products Projects and at the National Irrigation Research Station.

The GM collected from Zambia was

identified as *Orseolia oryzivora* by the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London. This species was identified from the collections in the Lake Chilwa area of

Malawi in 1974. These findings suggest that GM is distributed throughout the Guinea savannas of Africa. □

Chemical control of grasshoppers in Pakistan

M. A. Zafar, senior subject matter specialist in plant protection, Agricultural Adaptive Research Farm (AARF), Sheikhpura, Pakistan

In some years, grasshopper *Hieroglyphus* spp. cause significant losses to rice nurseries and crops in Pakistan. In 1982 we tested four dusts in doses generally recommended in treatments for grasshopper control at AARF.

Grasshoppers were collected from rice fields and reared at room temperature to achieve a large population of adults of uniform age and size. The dusts were cotton dust (6.3% BHC + 10.4% DDT + 83.3% sulfur), BHC 10%, 1:3 mixture of BHC 10% + DDT 10%, and carbaryl 10%. They were sprinkled on the grasshoppers and rice leaves. In the first trial, 100 grasshoppers were kept in a glass jar without food for 24 h, then were released on fresh food. In the second trial grasshoppers were caged on dusted leaves of

Grasshopper control with different insecticide dusts.^a AARF, Pakistan.

Dust	Dosage	Mortality (%) at indicated hours after treatment				
		1	3	6	12	24
	<i>g/100 grasshoppers</i>	<i>Direct dusting on grasshoppers</i>				
Cotton dust ^b	10	13.7	100	100	100	100
BHC 10%	10	22.3	100	100	100	100
BHC 10% + DDT 10% 1:3 mixture	10	18.0	100	100	100	100
Carbaryl 10%	10	16.3	100	100	100	100
Untreated control	—	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.6 ^a	0.0 ^a	1.3 ^a
LSD at 5%		7.4	20.9	21.3	28.6	16.8
	<i>kg ai/ha</i>	<i>Feeding on dust-impregnated nursery leaves</i>				
Cotton dust ^b	7.20	3.0	42.7	85.0	100	100
BHC 10%	0.75	8.7	49.7	88.3	100	100
BHC 10% + DDT 10% 1:3 mixture.	0.31 + 0.94	5.0	41.0	76.3	100	100
Carbaryl 10%	2.00	8.3	46.3	81.7	100	100
Untreated control	—	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.3 ^a	1.6 ^a	1.3 ^a
LSD at 5%		6.0	9.3	13.7	15.4	33.8

^aIn each column, averages followed by common letters are significantly similar at 95% level of confidence. ^bCotton dust is a brand name for the mixture of BHC + DDT + sulfur (3:5:40); the dose of 7.2 kg ai/ha is based on the 48% active ingredient in the formulation.

plants. Insect mortality was recorded 1, 3, 6, 12, and 24 h after treatment. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications.

With direct dusting, all grasshoppers died in 3 h. With foliar dusting, they died in 12 h. All the dusts were effective (see table). □

Entomophaga grylli destruction of locust *Oxya-hyla intricata* in Vietnam

J. Weiser, V. Matha, N. D. Tryachov, and I. Gelbic, Institute of Entomology, Academy of Science, Prague, Czechoslovakia

The fungus *E. grylli* (Fres.) Batko is the most common Entomophthorales fungus and often is associated with locust and grasshopper outbreaks. Data from Southeast Asia describe an outbreak of *E. grylli* in a *Patanga succinata* population on maize east of Lopburi Province in Thailand. By the end of the rainy season, the fungus had destroyed 90% of the locust population and was found in 9 other acridid pests in Thailand.

1. Germinating conidia of *E. grylli* on the wing of *O. intricata*
Scale = 10 µm.

O. intricata Stål is widely distributed in Southeast Asia — Burma, Thailand, Vietnam, West Malaysia — and some parts of South China. It damages rice and several other crops.

In autumn 1983, dense *O. intricata* populations seriously damaged rice around Hanoi, Vietnam. *E. grylli* infected 85-90% adults and nymphs, which died on the plants. Masses of conidiophores